

A Tensor Train-Based Low-Rank Approximation for Monte Carlo Tallies Compression

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ABSTRACT

The memory requirements associated with tally data in whole-core Monte Carlo (MC) depletion and multiphysics simulations are often substantial. This work provides a preliminary evaluation of using Tensor Train (TT)-based low-rank approximation to compress tally data during MC simulations by representing the tallies in TT format. To achieve this, we developed an in-house MC code in Python that solves the multigroup neutron transport problem and employs the `ttorch` library to convert tally data into the TT representation. The approach is tested on two simplified three-dimensional reactor benchmark problems to assess compression performance. Results show that the TT format can reduce the memory footprint of MC tally data by more than two orders of magnitude, typically achieving over 500-fold compression for the test problems considered, particularly when the tallies exhibit symmetry and smoothness corresponding to low-rank tensor structures. This compression approach can substantially reduce memory demands in MC high-fidelity reactor simulations, potentially making large-scale depletion and multiphysics analyses more practical.

Keywords: Monte Carlo, Tensor Train format, Low-rank approximation, Tally data compression

1. INTRODUCTION

Recent advancements in high-performance computing capabilities have made whole-core, multi-physics, and depletion analyses using Monte Carlo (MC) methods increasingly feasible [1, 2, 3]. Several reactor benchmarks, particularly for Pressurized Water Reactors (PWRs), have been released to assess the performance and accuracy of current high-fidelity simulation codes [4, 5]. Despite these developments, several challenges remain, particularly in the context of whole-core MC depletion simulations coupled with multi-physics calculations.

One of the primary concerns is the substantial memory demand associated with these simulations [6, 7]. In depletion calculations, it is necessary to tally multiple reaction rates for all nuclides within the fuel material across discretized spatial cells. Achieving high-fidelity solutions requires fine spatial discretization both in radial and axial directions. However, such discretization could significantly increase memory requirements, presenting a major bottleneck for large-scale MC multi-physics and depletion simulations.

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This memory requirement becomes particularly challenging when porting these simulations into graphics processing units (GPUs) [8, 9]. While GPUs offer massive parallelism, their on-board memory is typically smaller than that of host CPUs. Therefore, efficient memory management is crucial to enable scalable, whole-core MC multi-physics and depletion simulations, especially on GPU-accelerated platforms.

In this study, we investigate a tensor train-based low-rank approximation for reducing the memory footprint of MC tallies. The method is inspired by image compression techniques, which leverage low-rank structures in data to achieve high compression ratios with minimal information loss. Similarly, MC tallies often form high-dimensional tensors, which in some cases exhibit correlations that can be exploited in a low-rank tensor-train representation. To test this concept, we developed an in-house multi-group MC code for slab geometry, named **mcpy**, and applied the tensor-train-based compression to two test problems to assess its effectiveness in reducing tally storage requirements without incurring accuracy losses beyond the statistical uncertainties of the tallies.

2. TENSOR TRAIN LOW-RANK APPROXIMATION

A Tensor Train (TT) format [10], also known as the Matrix Product State (MPS) representation in quantum physics, provides a compact way to represent high-dimensional tensors as a sequence of smaller three-dimensional tensors, referred to as *TT cores*. This format is widely employed for low-rank approximation of multi-dimensional data, effectively mitigating the "curse of dimensionality." Previous studies have explored the application of the TT format to neutron transport problems; however, most existing studies have focused primarily on deterministic transport solvers [11, 12].

We begin the methodology for the tensor-train-based low-rank approximation of MC tallies by introducing the TT concept, followed by an explanation of its application to the low-rank approximation of MC tallies. Finally, we describe its implementation in our in-house MC code.

2.1. Tensor Train Format

A tensor $\mathcal{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{n_1 \times \dots \times n_d}$ can be represented in the TT format by decomposing it into a sequence of d three-dimensional core tensors $\mathcal{G}_k \in \mathbb{R}^{r_{k-1} \times n_k \times r_k}$, for $k = 1, \dots, d$. The scalars r_k are referred to as the TT ranks of the decomposition, with first and last ranks are fixed to $r_0 = r_d = 1$. Each entry of the tensor \mathcal{A} can then be computed as

$$\mathcal{A}(i_1, \dots, i_d) = \sum_{\alpha_1=1}^{r_1} \dots \sum_{\alpha_{d-1}=1}^{r_{d-1}} \mathcal{G}_1(1, i_1, \alpha_1) \mathcal{G}_2(\alpha_1, i_2, \alpha_2) \dots \mathcal{G}_d(\alpha_{d-1}, i_d, 1), \quad (1)$$

where (i_1, \dots, i_d) denotes the index of the tensor entry.

Alternatively, the entries of \mathcal{A} can be expressed in a more compact matrix form as

$$\mathcal{A}(i_1, \dots, i_d) = \mathcal{G}_1[i_1] \mathcal{G}_2[i_2] \dots \mathcal{G}_d[i_d], \quad (2)$$

where $\mathcal{G}_k[i_k]$ denotes the i_k -th slice of the k -th TT core along its second dimension, resulting in a matrix $\mathcal{G}_k[i_k] \in \mathbb{R}^{r_{k-1} \times r_k}$.

It can be observed that, instead of storing $n_1 n_2 \dots n_d$ elements as in the full tensor, the TT format requires storing only

$$\sum_{k=1}^d n_k r_{k-1} r_k. \quad (3)$$

If all dimensions satisfy $n_k = n$ and all TT-ranks satisfy $r_k = r$, the storage scales as $\mathcal{O}(dnr^2)$, which is linear in the dimension d , in contrast to the exponential $\mathcal{O}(n^d)$ complexity of the full tensor

representation. It should be noted, however, that the TT format may require more storage than the original tensor in cases where the tensor is nearly full-rank or when a very small decomposition tolerance is imposed.

The TT decomposition can be efficiently computed using the TT-SVD algorithm. In this method, the tensor is reshaped sequentially into a series of two-dimensional matrices, referred to as *unfoldings*. A truncated singular value decomposition (SVD) is then applied to each unfolding in succession, and the TT cores \mathcal{G}_k are extracted from the resulting SVD factors. This procedure resembles a recursive application of the matrix SVD along the tensor dimensions.

2.2. Low-Rank Approximation in TT Format

One of the key advantages of the TT format is its ability to construct efficient low-rank approximations of high-dimensional tensors. The TT-SVD algorithm achieves this by performing a sequence of truncated SVDs, where singular values below a prescribed local threshold ϵ are discarded. The resulting approximation error, measured in the Frobenius norm, satisfies the bound

$$\|\mathcal{A} - \mathcal{A}_{\text{TT}}\|_F \leq \epsilon \sqrt{d-1} \|\mathcal{A}\|_F, \quad (4)$$

where \mathcal{A}_{TT} denotes the truncated TT approximation of the original tensor \mathcal{A} . This estimate implies that the TT-SVD algorithm produces a *quasi-optimal* approximation, in the sense that the global approximation error is explicitly controlled by the chosen truncation threshold ϵ and grows at most proportionally to $\sqrt{d-1}$.

To illustrate the potential of data compression using the TT format, consider a tensor $\mathcal{A} \in \mathbb{R}^{100 \times 100 \times 100}$. Storing this tensor in full would require $n^d = 10^6$ entries. However, if \mathcal{A} has a low-rank structure such that the TT ranks satisfy $r_k = 5$ for given error threshold ϵ , then the TT representation would require storage of only $\mathcal{O}(dnr^2) = 7500$ elements. This corresponds to a compression ratio of approximately 133.3, representing a substantial reduction in memory usage and demonstrating the efficiency of the TT format for data compression.

2.3. Implementation

We developed `mcpy` to evaluate low-rank approximations in the TT format for compressing MC tallies. `mcpy` is a Python-based Monte Carlo code developed to solve multigroup neutron transport eigenvalue problems in slab geometries. The `ttorch` library [13] was employed to convert tensors into TT format and perform arithmetic operations in this representation. `ttorch` is an open-source Python library built on top of PyTorch, designed for tensor network modeling and learning. It supports multiple tensor decomposition formats, including CP, Tucker, and Tensor Train, under a unified interface.

Both the tally scores and their corresponding sums of squares are converted into the TT format and accumulated using TT addition at the end of each active cycle. The error threshold is set to $\epsilon = 0.01$ for the conversion of the scores and their sums of squares into the TT format. This error threshold is chosen to ensure that the compression error remains within the expected statistical uncertainties of the tally results. To prevent the explosion of TT ranks during tally accumulation, TT rounding is applied after each TT addition. In Section 3, we demonstrate the resulting compression ratios achieved using the TT format.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Test Problems

Two test problems are considered to evaluate the effectiveness of the TT format in compressing MC tallies. Both involve simplified three-dimensional, two-group reactor core problems: one with control

Figure 1. Geometry of the three-dimensional reactor core for the ROD_IN test problem.

Table I. Two-group macroscopic cross sections used in the test problems (no upscattering)

Macroscopic XS	Core	Reflector	Control Rod
Σ_{t1}	0.2351	0.2290	0.2805
Σ_{t2}	0.8928	1.1497	1.8449
$\nu\Sigma_{f1}$	0.0054	0.0000	0.0000
$\nu\Sigma_{f2}$	0.1043	0.0000	0.0000
$\Sigma_{s1 \rightarrow 1}$	0.2093	0.1995	0.0677
$\Sigma_{s1 \rightarrow 2}$	0.0174	0.0290	0.0001
$\Sigma_{s2 \rightarrow 2}$	0.8261	1.1202	0.3523

rods inserted and one without. These configurations are hereafter referred to as ROD_IN and ROD_OUT, respectively. Figure 1 illustrates the radial and axial views of the quarter-core reactor geometry for the ROD_IN case.

The quarter active core has dimensions of $50 \times 50 \times 80$ cm and is surrounded by reflector regions extending 10 cm in both the radial and axial directions, resulting in a total quarter-core size of $60 \times 60 \times 100$ cm. The control rod assembly has a cross-sectional area of 10×10 cm and is inserted to a depth of 30 cm from the top of the upper reflector. In the ROD_OUT case, the regions occupied by the control rod assembly in the core and reflector are replaced by core and reflector materials, respectively.

Table I presents the two-group macroscopic cross sections (XS) used in both reactor core configurations, with no upscattering considered. Some of these XS data were adopted from Takeda's small Light Water Reactor benchmark [14]. Table II summarizes the key simulation parameters employed in the Monte Carlo runs.

To evaluate the accuracy and efficiency of the TT-based compressed tallies, both pointwise and global relative error metrics are employed. The pointwise relative error for the i -th tally value is defined as

$$\varepsilon_i = \frac{x_i - \hat{x}_i}{x_i}, \quad x_i \neq 0, \quad (5)$$

Table II. Monte Carlo simulation parameters for the test problems

Parameter	
Number of particle histories per cycle	5×10^5
Number of inactive cycles	50
Number of active cycles	150

Table III. Comparison of numerical results for the test problems.

Parameter	ROD_OUT case	ROD_IN case
OpenMC k_{eff}	1.09894 ± 0.00008	1.09518 ± 0.00008
mcpy k_{eff}	1.09908 ± 0.00008	1.09508 ± 0.00008
Global relative error (uncompressed flux)	0.025	0.092
Global relative error (TT-compressed flux)	0.019	0.089

where x_i and \hat{x}_i denote the reference solutions and tally values from mcpy, respectively. The global relative error is expressed in terms of ℓ_2 norm as

$$E_{\text{rel}} = \frac{\|\mathbf{x} - \hat{\mathbf{x}}\|_2}{\|\mathbf{x}\|_2}. \quad (6)$$

In this study, the reference solutions are obtained using the OpenMC Monte Carlo code [15]. The compression ratio of the tallies is quantified as the ratio between the number of elements in the full tensor representation and those in the TT representation:

$$\text{Compression Ratio} = \frac{\text{Number of entries in full tensor format}}{\text{Number of entries in TT format}}. \quad (7)$$

A higher compression ratio indicates a more efficient representation of the tally data in the TT format. Finally, the memory requirement is evaluated as the product of the memory required per entry and the total number of stored entries.

3.2. Numerical Results and Analysis

For both the ROD_IN and ROD_OUT benchmark problems, a mesh tally was conducted using a $60 \times 60 \times 100$ spatial mesh and a two-group energy to estimate the scalar flux distribution. In this study, the collision estimator was employed for tallying the flux. Table III presents and compares the numerical results obtained from OpenMC and mcpy for both test cases.

As shown in Table III, the effective multiplication factors computed by mcpy closely match those obtained from OpenMC, with differences well within 2σ . Furthermore, the global relative error in the uncompressed flux tally is below 3.0% for the ROD_OUT case and approximately 9.0% for the ROD_IN case. Similar trends are observed for the TT-based compressed flux, indicating that the TT-based method preserves accuracy with a marginal increase in error.

Figure 2 shows the radially averaged axial thermal flux distribution obtained from both OpenMC and mcpy for the ROD_IN case, along with their comparative results. The results indicate excellent agreement across most of the domain. Notably, the TT-compressed flux exhibits slightly higher relative errors (approximately 2.0%) near the top and bottom boundaries of the reactor core. Nevertheless, the TT-based compressed tally provides flux estimates that are comparably accurate to those from the uncompressed method, demonstrating that TT-based compressed tallies can provide reliably accurate tally results.

Figure 2. Comparison of radially averaged axial thermal flux distributions from OpenMC and *mcpy* for the ROD_IN case. The label *mcpy_TT* denotes the TT-based compressed flux.

Table IV. Compression efficiency of the TT format for storing flux tally data.

Parameter	ROD_OUT case	ROD_IN case
Compression ratio of tally sum	1052	598
Compression ratio of sum of squared tallies	3243	1281
Memory usage (uncompressed tally)	11.5 MB	11.5 MB
Memory usage (TT-compressed tally)	7.3 KB	14.1 KB
Overall compression ratio	1588	815

The compression ratios for the *tally sum*, the *sum of squared tallies*, and the *overall memory efficiency* are summarized in Table IV. The *tally sum* corresponds to the accumulation of tally scorings over all active cycles and is used to compute the final tally mean. The *sum of squared tallies* represents the accumulation of squared scorings over active cycles and is required for estimating the tally variance or standard deviation. The *overall compression ratio* is defined as the ratio of the memory required to store the uncompressed tally data (including both the tally sum and the sum of squared tallies) to the memory required to store their TT-compressed representations. Note that this metric reflects the compression efficiency of the tally data only and does not represent a global compression ratio for the entire simulation.

As shown in Table IV, the TT-based MC tally compression achieves highly efficient memory reduction, exceeding two orders of magnitude in all cases, with overall compression ratios greater than 500-fold for both problems. The ROD_OUT case, in particular, exhibits a higher compression ratio due to the lower-rank structure of its flux distribution, which arises from the geometric symmetry of the problem and smoothness of the tally distribution. These results demonstrate that TT-based tally compression is an effective approach for substantially reducing the memory footprint of MC tally data without significant loss of accuracy.

Although high compression ratios were eventually achieved, they were not attained at the beginning of the active cycles. In the early active cycles, when only a small number of tallies had been sampled, the compression ratios for both the tally sum and the sum of squared tallies remained close to unity. As more tallies were accumulated over successive cycles, a low-rank structure began to emerge in the tally data, enabling significantly higher compression ratios, as illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Evolution of compression ratio over active cycles for the ROD_OUT (left) and ROD_IN (right) cases.

In addition, the use of TT-based tally compression resulted in a moderate increase in simulation time. Specifically, for both the ROD_OUT and ROD_IN cases, the simulation time with compression was approximately 1.36 times longer than that without compression. These two aspects: delayed compression effectiveness and increased runtime, present opportunities for further optimization in the future studies.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This study presents a preliminary investigation into the application of TT-based low-rank approximation for compressing MC tallies. To demonstrate the feasibility of the proposed TT-based tally compression approach, an in-house code, *mcpy*, was developed and tested on two three-dimensional, two-group reactor core benchmark problems.

The results indicate that TT-based tally compression achieves highly efficient data reduction for both test cases, with overall compression ratios exceeding 500-fold. The method is particularly effective for tally distributions exhibiting a low-rank structure, such as symmetric or smooth tally distributions. However, two challenges remain: the delayed compression efficiency during the early active cycles, and the moderate increase in simulation time associated with the TT-based implementation. These issues highlight opportunities for further improvement in future works.

Overall, TT-based tally compression demonstrates strong potential to significantly reduce memory requirements in high-fidelity MC reactor simulations, thereby enabling more practical large-scale depletion and multiphysics analyses.

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